
STATISTICAL REVIEW OF ECONOMIC TRANSACTION IN COVID-19 PANDEMIC OF SINDHUDURG SEAFORT

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Introduction:

Today Geography includes multidisciplinary approach; many branches are created by this subject. The tourism business is major source of Indian economy. Western cost of India having so much tourist points are observed, these points are attracts to the tourists from India and abroad. There are big economic transitions created through tourism business. Sindhudurg fort is the major source of economic transaction which giving so many employment generation and development of the concern place. In summer season number of visitors is high than the rainy season, in winter season students are visits to that fort, therefore the daily economic transaction is high in summer season. Average number of visitors of Sindhudurg fort is 6059 per day, but from March 2019 to end of 2021 there is very less numbers of tourists are visited to the Sindhudurg fort due to Covid-19 pandemic. The economic transaction is

very less in that Covid-19 period. Considering this fact we have taken here to study an impact of Covid-19 on economic transaction of Sindhudurg fort.

Scope of the Study:

Adoption of change is the natural behavior of human being. Each and every people naturally want to visit the new or unknown place. Sindhudurg fort is an important historical place which wants to conserve it. There are 6059 visitors are visited per day to fort. Original structure of the fort is not observed today. The walls are broken few places of the fort. It's necessary to conserve the fort as a historical memento.

Objective:

To analyses an impact of covid-19 pandemic an economic transaction of Sindhudurg sea fort.

Study region:

The Sindhudurg fort is chosen for the study. It's located near Malvan sea coast

of Arabian Sea in western side of Maharashtra state.

Location of Sindhudurg Seafort**Data Collection and Methodology:**

The concern data has been collected from field work, visited to Sindhudurg fort ticket counter and the related information is collected through an interview and fillup the questionnaire from tourists as well as visitors. The secondary data also taken from ticket counter

register. Proper statistical and cartographic techniques are used wherever necessary.

Results and Discussion:

Table no. 1 reveals that the domestic visitors are proportionally high then the foreign visitors. From December to March the visitors are accordingly grown with compare to the previous months. Changing

climatic condition is basic reason behind that. In holidays there are hues amount of visitors are visited to the Sindhudurg sea

fort (Kapur & Gupta, 2007). For the students Rs. 40/- per head

Table 1: Month wise average Domestic and Foreign visitors in Sindhudurg sea fort
(Year- 2016 to 2019)

Months	Domestic	Percentage	Transaction '000' Rs.	Percentage	Foreign	Percentage	Transaction '000' Rs.	Percentage
April	196152	8.869114635	13731	8.8693529	1202	9.64996789	240	9.63468487
May	185804	8.401224436	13006	8.401049	1185	9.51348748	237	9.5142513
June	177755	8.037284718	12443	8.0373868	934	7.49839435	187	7.50702529
July	156744	7.087261432	10972	7.08721433	835	6.70359666	167	6.70413489
Aug	172741	7.810574101	12092	7.81066312	734	5.89274245	147	5.90124448
Sept	161259	7.291409503	11288	7.29133024	702	5.63583815	140	5.62023284
Oct	153634	6.946641165	10754	6.9464002	686	5.507386	137	5.49979928
Nov	157341	7.114255097	11013	7.11369773	752	6.03725112	150	6.02167804
Dec	214003	9.676256878	14980	9.67612748	1384	11.11111111	277	11.1200321
Jan	206422	9.333478023	14449	9.33313525	1370	10.9987155	274	10.9995986
Feb	222744	10.07148574	15592	10.0714406	1334	10.7096981	267	10.7185869
Mar	207031	9.361014275	14492	9.36091051	1338	10.7418112	268	10.7587314
Total	2211630	100	154814	100	12456	100	2491	100

Source: Compiled and calculated by authors

Entry fee has been charged with submitting their bonafied certificate from the concern institution. The average domestic visitors during the period given in the table 1 are 6059 per day. The number of foreign visitors are high in the month of December whereas low in September, the average no. of foreign visitors 34 per day and around Rs. 25 lacks fees generated from the foreign visitors. Rs. 1548 lacks fees generated from the domestic visitors.

According to table-2, 2019 to 2021 in these period only Domestic visitors visited to fort. Foreign visitors are zero in this period because this was affected by Covid-19 pandemic. 2019 to 2021 per head ticket was 50Rs. only 10Rs. was increased of lack of foreign visitors (Gaikwad, etal., 2015). In April month visitors are very low because Maharashtra Government proclaimed "Curfew and The Communication Ban" in 23 March 2020

May to March 2021 increased Domestic visitors after lift of curfew.

In the year 2021 to 2022 both Domestic and Foreign visitors visited to fort. It was the effect of the lift of curfew and Communication Ban by Maharashtra

Government. As well as world was relaxation was for all the people that why the foreign visitors were increased in this period.

Table 2: Monthwise average Domestic and Foreign visitors in Sindhudurg sea fort

Year- 2019 to 2021		
Months	Domestic visitors	Foreign visitors
April	817	00
May	1240	00
June	1580	00
July	1420	00
Aug	1144	00
Sept	959	00
Oct	1325	00
Nov	2028	00
Dec	2530	00
Jan	2435	00
Feb	2290	00
Mar	1120	00
Total		

Year- 2021 to 2022		
Months	Domestic visitors	Foreign visitors
April	5235	142
May	7454	458
June	8475	544
July	6754	894
Aug	6254	653
Sept	7425	754
Oct	7852	745
Nov	8325	820
Dec	28234	1004
Jan	105874	20024
Feb	112214	21124
Mar	161241	24999
Total	465337	72161

Source: Compiled and calculated by authors

Conclusions:

1. In the Covid-19 pandemic period only domestic visitors were visited to fort.
2. In the relaxation in Curfew and communication ban the foreigner visitors started to visit fort, as well as we founds growth in domestic visitors.

Recommendation:

In this period Government could do the restructure of the broken things

on fort as well as the cleaning of the fort.

References:

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